

24 case of the study area “Dehesa Boyal” in Ávila (Spain) which includes both these habitats
25 in the Natura 2000 network. Moreover, traditional timber harvesting plans do not take
26 account of the new objectives required for these Natura 2000 sites, which attempt to
27 ensure biodiversity and recreational uses instead of simply focusing on timber
28 production.

29 This paper therefore proposes a flexible methodology for managing Natura 2000
30 forest sites by stands for timber harvesting plans, adapted to sustainable forest
31 management and to the new requirements. The methodology has two phases. The first
32 “Division of the forest area into stands” defines homogeneous areas in terms of forestry
33 criteria and future management (stands). The second phase “Conservation status
34 assessment of stands” evaluates the conservation status of each previously classified
35 stands considering a series of factors such as: vital functions, restoration, floral richness
36 and structure. A total value integrating the conservation status of stands is then calculated
37 for the habitat. The proposed methodology provides forest managers with a good
38 knowledge of the territory and subsequently allows them to take accurate conservation
39 measures in order to maintain the biodiversity in a favourable conservation status.

40 This paper applies this methodology to the forest site “Dehesa Boyal” in Ávila.
41 Based on the results, forestry measures are then planned by stands to ensure the
42 biodiversity of these specific habitats. Conversion of coppice forest to high forest by
43 thinning (low-intensity thinning of sprouts, less than 35% of the basal area) is proposed in
44 the *Quercus pyrenaica* habitat (high polewood, sapling and coppice tall shrubs) during

45 the first fifteen years. Some pruning is proposed as a forestry treatment to ensure
46 biodiversity in the *Quercus ilex subsp. rotundifolia* forest habitat.

47 Key words: Natura 2000, biodiversity, forest management, conservation status, habitats,
48 *Quercus pyrenaica*.

49 **Introduction**

50 In the early 1970s there was a surge of concern regarding global environmental
51 degradation in the form of deforestation, loss of biological diversity, climate change and
52 extinction of species, among others. These concerns led to a series of international
53 conferences (United Nations Conference on Environment and Development) conventions
54 (Convention on Biological Diversity) and agreements whereby nations set up frameworks
55 to deal with these issues and thereby ensure biodiversity (Mace and Baillie, 2007). The
56 European Union adopted legislation to protect the most seriously threatened species and
57 habitats across Europe: firstly, the Birds Directive 79/409/EEC and later the Habitats
58 Directive 92/43/EEC (Martinez et al., 2007). At the heart of both these Directives is the
59 creation of a network of sites called “Natura 2000” which represents one of the EU’s
60 main responses to this new framework (Maiorano et al., 2007; Cantarello, 2008; Varela et
61 al., 2008). This network includes Special Protection Areas (**SPAs**) for birds, and Special
62 Areas of Conservation (**SACs**) for habitats, which in a previous phase before the
63 implementation of management plans are known as Spaces of Community Interest
64 (**SCIs**), to provide endangered animals, plants and habitats with increased protection
65 (Weber and Christophersen, 2002; Martinez et al., 2007). European Member States are
66 required by the Habitats Directive to establish the necessary conservation measures and

67 management plans (Ostermann, 1998) to ensure the favourable conservation status of
68 natural habitats (Article 1.e) and species (Article 1.i) in these areas (Council Directive,
69 1992). Furthermore, some specific measures relating to sustainable forest management
70 have been developed within an international framework, such as Forest Principles and
71 within a European framework, such as the Ministerial Conferences on the Protection of
72 Forests in Europe (Andersson et al., 2000;Mayer and Rametsteiner, 2004).

73 This entire new framework, based on concern about loss of biodiversity and the
74 idea of ensuring a sustainable forest management requires forestry experts to focus on
75 new management methods (Szaro and Johston, 1996). Nowadays, timber harvesting takes
76 place alongside other activities with ecological and recreational objectives (Tarrega *et al.*,
77 2006) and timber harvesting projects and regeneration methods must therefore comply
78 with new production goals and environmental services (Montes *et al.*, 2004).

79 The method of regeneration by stands was first proposed by Judeich, a teacher at
80 the Tharand School (Germany) between 1871 and 1893. He criticises the block methods
81 used up to that time because of their rigid forestry management techniques (González
82 Molina *et al.*, 2006). He proposed that each stand (permanent management unit) should
83 have its own regeneration period and rotation age in order to provide greater flexibility.
84 The method was not accorded much importance at the time because in most cases the
85 main concern was timber production, and not the guarantee of biodiversity as is required
86 today (Bissonette and Storch, 2003). However, more recently this method of regeneration
87 is being applied with some modifications in certain Natura 2000 areas in Spain (González
88 Molina *et al.*, 2006) as it is suited to their requirements.

89 Therefore, in view of the flexibility of stands, this paper proposes a methodology
90 for managing Natura 2000 forest sites by stands, designed to support forest management
91 in this network. It has two phases. The first phase characterises the study area in
92 homogeneous parts (stands) with the latest technologies (Geographic Information System
93 and Remote Sensing) and detailed fieldwork. The second phase evaluates the
94 conservation status of each stand. The conservation status of the habitat is then obtained
95 by integrating these values. This assessment is an essential component in Natura 2000
96 sites (Ostermann, 1998;European Commission, 2006) as it is required by the Habitats
97 Directive. Various attempts have been made using numerical quantifiers and indicators
98 (Maggi et al., 2005;Smelko and Fabrika, 2007;Cantarello, 2008) in some cases using
99 G.I.S and remote sensing (Boteva et al., 2004;Langanke et al., 2007;Buchanan et al.,
100 2008;Pringle et al., 2009), and in most cases dealing with large scales (Forster et al.,
101 2007;Velázquez-Saornil, 2008).

102 Finally, forestry management measures are recommended for maintaining the
103 favourable conservation status of the study area. These measures include consumption of
104 the forest resources in such as way as to satisfy the objectives of both landowners and
105 society (Davis and Jonhson, 1987;Brunson and Huntsinger, 2008;Irvine et al., 2009).

106

107 **Methods and techniques**

108

109 **Area description**

110 The study was carried out in the public forested land within the Natura 2000
111 Network, called “Dehesa Boyal” (Tejera-Gimeno and Núñez-Martí, 2007), which
112 belongs to the Region of Castilla y León in central Spain (Figure 1).

113 This forest territory (815 ha) is included in the Natura 2000 Network as part of the
114 **SPA** ES0000186: “Pinares del bajo Alberche” as it is in an area of importance for black
115 stork (*Ciconia nigra*) and is also part of a recovery plan for imperial eagle (*Aquila*
116 *adalberti*). Furthermore, it is in the **SCI** ES4110114: “Pinares del bajo Alberche” as four
117 of its habitats are listed in Annex I of the Habitats Directive (Council Directive,
118 1992;Bartolomé, 2005):

- 119 • **Habitat I: 9230- Galicio-Portuguese oak woods with *Quercus pyrenaica*, *rebollo***
120 ***oak*. (Mediterranean deciduous forests).**
- 121 • **Habitat II: 9340- *Quercus ilex* subsp. *rotundifolia* forests. (Mediterranean**
122 ***sclerophyllous* forests).**

123 Both species, *Quercus pyrenaica* and *Quercus ilex*, have traditionally been pruned
124 and felled to provide firewood and cattle forage (Montoya, 1982). This specific area was
125 clear-cut every 12-20 years. Coppice management stimulates new sprouts, which are very
126 palatable to livestock (Valbuena-Carabana *et al.*, 2008). However, nowadays firewood is
127 no longer extracted.

- 128 • **Habitats III: 3170*** Mediterranean temporary ponds and **Habitats IV: 6220*** Pseudo-
129 steppe with grasses and annuals of Thero-Brachypodietea.

130 Previous firewood extraction and grazing in the area has formed a coppice forest.
131 Around 180 horses, 1100 goats, 900 sheep and 190 cows graze in the study area
132 throughout the year, distributed over the different seasons. As a result of this, most fallen
133 acorns are eaten by cattle, and saplings are rare. There is therefore a lack of sexual
134 regeneration, and reproduction ultimately occurs through shoots from roots or stumps
135 (Serrada-Hierro *et al.*, 1994), thus limiting biodiversity.

136 **Methodology**

137 The methodology for managing Natura 2000 forest sites by stands has two phases
138 and is aimed at supporting forest management. The first phase consists of dividing the
139 forest area into stands, and characterising the study area in homogeneous parts; and the
140 second phase provides an assessment of the conservation status of the stands. Both phases
141 are based on European conservation requirements and the experience of our research
142 group in implementing Natura 2000 timber harvesting projects (Tejera-Gimeno and
143 Núñez-Martí, 2007).

144 **a) Division of the forest area into stands.**

145 First, we define the concept of “stand” in order to clarify its correct use. A stand is
146 a temporary forest management unit (the last division of the inventory). The main
147 purpose of this phase is to demarcate the stands in the study area. This first phase consists
148 of five parts:
149

150 The goal of the preliminary fieldwork is to obtain an overview of the different **(i)**
151 types of repeated homogeneous species formations. Then, based on the forest features
152 and possible future forest management **(ii)** the criteria are selected for separating the
153 stands (Tables 1 and 2). In the next step, cartography information, aerial photos and
154 Geographic Information System (G.I.S) maps are collected to obtain the most detailed
155 knowledge of the area. All the previous information is used to elaborate a draft of the
156 possible stands before going back to the field. The next phase of the fieldwork is aimed at
157 identifying the types of stands in the field according to the chosen criteria and the G.I.S.
158 information; the remote sensing map, which divides the area into polygons, is a useful
159 tool as it enables polygons to be easily joined or separated. Once the stands are

160 demarcated, the next step is (iv) to choose the type of inventory –either systematic or
161 qualitative– to be implemented in each stand. The last phase of the fieldwork is to check
162 the correct location of the stands and make (v) a standard document for each stand,
163 containing all the qualitative and quantitative information.

164 **b) Assessment of the conservation status of stands.**

165 This phase first evaluates the conservation status of the previously determined
166 stands. The status is assessed by expert forest managers from "3" to "1", where "3" is
167 good or favourable status, "2" is inconvenient and "1" is poor. The assessment factors are
168 based on the definition of the favourable conservation status of habitats (Article 1.e) and
169 species (Article 1.i) in the Habitats Directive and the Natura 2000 Standard Data Form
170 for site monitoring (European Commission, 1995). Four factors are considered:

- 171 • Vital functions (f₁): considers vitality and state of health. It evaluates the best (3) or
172 worst (1) capacity for carrying out natural processes (Hazell and Gustafsson, 1999).
- 173 • Restoration (f₂): evaluates the capacity of habitats to recover when the applied action
174 or pressure is completed (Barbati *et al.*, 2002).
- 175 • Floral richness (f₃): evaluates the presence of a large number of typical species from
176 each habitat (Batary *et al.*, 2007;Castellarini *et al.*, 2007).
- 177 • Forest structure (f₄): value (1) corresponds to a regular structure which is not
178 conducive to a good conservation status. Value (3) corresponds to an irregular
179 structure, with different age classes, considered favourable for biodiversity (Pelissier
180 and Goreaud, 2001;Barbati *et al.*, 2002;de Warnaffe and Devillez, 2002).

181 The conservation status of the different types of stands (\bar{s}_j) is calculated for each stand
182 (j) as the weighted average:

183 - ($\bar{s}_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{w_i \cdot f_i}{n}$), where n = number of factors described (f_i) and (w_i) =
184 weight of each factor, where $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$.

185 Next, the value of the entire habitat conservation status is calculated by integrating
186 the previous values:

187 The conservation status of the habitat (H) when composed by different stands is obtained
188 by the weighted average of the conservation status of the different types of stands (\bar{s}_j)
189 and their areas (A_j):

190 - ($H = \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\bar{s}_j \cdot A_j}{A}$), where ($A = \sum_{j=1}^p A_j$) and p = number of stands in the
191 habitat.

192 When the habitat is composed by only one stand, $H = \bar{s}$. The final values \bar{v} are listed in
193 Table 3.

194
195 **Results**

196 Regarding the application of the methodology to the study area, the first phase,
197 consisting of the division of the forest area into stands, comprises the following parts:

198 (i) Types of repeated homogeneous species formations: grassland, *Quercus pyrenaica* and
199 *Quercus ilex habitats* in different age classes.

200 (ii) Criteria for separating stands (Table 1&2): diameter and future management (dbh).

201 Identification of types of stands in the field:

202 • **Habitat I: 9230- Galicio-Portuguese oak woods with *Quercus pyrenaica*, rebollo**
203 **oak.** This is divided into the following types of stands depicted in Figure 2, and
204 described below:

- 205 ○ Oak shrubland: this type includes stump shoots (coppice shoots) and/or root
206 shoots (sprouts) under one metre high. It is very palatable to cattle. As a result, it
207 is continuously hedged and is low and irregular in shape, with poor vitality
208 (Barbour *et al.*, 2007). It is completely deteriorated and needs some
209 improvements.
- 210 ○ Low polewood: taller than one metre but with a dbh (diameter at breast height) <
211 10 cm. Considerable damage is found in this type due to browsing and intensive
212 grazing. Hedged and broken branches are the most common features.
- 213 ○ High polewood (10 cm <dbh<20 cm): in this kind of stand there are some trees
214 with an improved shape which are beginning to stand out from the rest of the
215 forest cover.
- 216 ○ Sapling (20 cm <dbh<35 cm): this stand is characterised by the widest trees in the
217 forest crop. Some of these trees have acorns. However continuous grazing by
218 cattle represents a serious problem for the survival of the acorns. In addition,
219 compacting by livestock hinders acorn regeneration.

220 ○ Coppice tall shrubs: grove of stump shoots (coppice shoots), taller than oak
221 shrubland (over one metre high) forming round scattered groups throughout the
222 grassland.

223 • **Habitat II: 9340- *Quercus ilex subsp. rotundifolia* forests.** Due to the reduced area
224 of this habitat in the study area and considering its future management, this habitat
225 includes different age classes in the same high forest stand.

226 • **Habitat III:** Both 3170* **Mediterranean temporary ponds** and **Habitat IV:6220***
227 **Pseudo-steppe with grasses and annuals of *Thero-Brachypodietea*** form the sole
228 stand with pasture.

229 (iv) Choosing the type of inventory: one systematic and qualitative inventory in each
230 forest stand.

231 (v) A standard document for each stand which includes: area, situation map, picture, type
232 of vegetation, description of the forest characteristics, description of damage, inventory
233 data and forest management proposal.

234 In the second phase, the conservation status is estimated using the guidelines
235 explained above. The results of the conservation status assessment are summarised in
236 Table 4 and displayed in Figure 3.

237 The values in **Habitat I** for the different stands described are as follows:

238 Oak shrubland and low pole stages: the vegetation in this kind of stand is very
239 palatable to livestock. Cattle graze there most of the time, eating the acorns and the young
240 sprouts which make them sprout again. This, added to its previous use for firewood

241 extraction, leads to its classification as a “coppice forest”, with asexual regeneration.
242 Vital functions scored value (1) due to the continuous hedging, which prevents normal
243 growth. Recovery is quick in low pole stages (2) and better in oak shrubland (3) in the
244 absence of pressure from cattle. Floral richness in both cases is relatively low (1) due to
245 the establishment of pasture instead of the typical cover of the habitat. The value of the
246 regular structure in these stands is (1). In this case, it was decided that the four factors
247 ($W_1 = W_2 = W_3 = W_4$) had the same importance and therefore the same weight. The
248 conservation status of these two stands is poor (C). Figure 4 shows the poor conservation
249 status evaluated with the proposed methodology.

250 Coppice tall shrub: the values for the floral and structural factors are similar to the
251 previous stands. However, as the trees are higher, this type of stand has fewer problems
252 with vital functions (2) and recovery capacity (2). Using the integration criteria, the final
253 value is (C).

254 Sapling: this type has no problems with vital functions and recovery (3). The trees
255 are tall and wide enough to protect themselves against any possible damage from grazing
256 and can therefore grow unhindered. However, regeneration is disturbed due to cattle,
257 which eat the acorns and lead to the absence of the desired samplings in the habitat.
258 Floral richness is higher (2) than in the stands above, as these areas are less intensively
259 grazed and hedged. There is therefore greater survival of other species and a less regular
260 structure (2). The conservation status of this stand is favourable or good (A), as shown in
261 Figure 5.

262 High polewood scores intermediate (2) values for all the factors described. The
263 final value for this stand is inconvenient (B).

264 The final conservation status of Habitat I (H_I) (Table 3) is poor (C), obtained by
265 the weighted average, taking into consideration the areas of the different types of
266 stands A_j .

267 For **Habitat II**, a single stand was designated due to the reduced study area. No
268 differences between age classes were made in this case. As this stand is located on a very
269 steep slope there is less presence of cattle. For this reason, vital functions are less
270 damaged (2) and floral richness and structure have intermediate values (2). The worst
271 aspect of this conservation status is its recovery, which is hindered by the slope (2). The
272 final conservation status of Habitat II (H_{II}) is inconvenient (B).

273 There is no assessment of **Habitat III** and **IV** as these are pasture habitats, and the
274 methodology focuses on forest sites.

275 **Discussion**

276
277 The application of the proposed methodology provides forest managers with a
278 detailed and accurate knowledge of the study area. Otherwise forest managers may
279 inadvertently compromise global biodiversity goals by unsuitable management methods
280 (Noss, 1999). The initial division of the forest area into stands accurately delimits the
281 homogeneous areas designated as stands in the terms defined (Figure 2). The G.I.S. map
282 of these stands provides managers with a meticulous description of the study area and its
283 location. These stands will be used as management units in the future. Another feature of
284 the methodology is that the elaboration of this G.I.S. map of the stands requires extensive
285 fieldwork and data treatment, after which planners are better prepared to provide values
286 for the application of the second phase, which requires forestry experience and a good
287 knowledge of the area.

288 Secondly, the assessment of the conservation status of the stands enables
289 decisions regarding the forest management in the area to be made more accurately and
290 easily (de Warnaffe and Devillez, 2002). Values of only 1, 2 and 3 are assigned in order
291 to avoid any possible intermediate values which do not alert managers to extreme
292 situations and would make the classification more subjective. The conservation status of
293 the different types of stands (\bar{s}) is calculated as an average in a general case. However,
294 different coefficients could be applied to the factors according to each case and particular
295 conditions. Previous works on this subject (Maggi et al., 2005; Smelko and Fabrika,
296 2007; Cantarello, 2008; Velázquez-Saornil, 2008) often assess the conservation status of
297 habitats or biotopes as a single value, without taking into consideration their different
298 parts (stands). Consequently, the habitat conservation value does not show the location of
299 unfavourable areas, unlike this methodology, which provides a detailed indication of the
300 location of possible problem areas to enable solutions to be provided.

301 Goals and measures to ensure biodiversity must be established with adequate
302 knowledge of the past, current, and potential future condition of the forest. In the case of
303 forests with history of intensive use by humans, it makes sense to monitor the progress
304 toward the recovery of the forest (Noss, 1999). Cattle owners have their own interests and
305 are not yet concerned about the importance of Natura 2000 (Li *et al.*, 2004). Their
306 livestock, cause of the poor conservation status, cannot be totally removed. Any solution
307 therefore needs to take account of the overall analysis and general circumstances of the
308 area in order to reach a sustainable agreement. Nowadays in Spain firewood is no longer
309 much in demand, and management therefore needs to focus on new environmental
310 services (Montes *et al.*, 2004). In view of this situation, the conversion of coppice forest

311 to high forest is commonly recommended by expert managers (Montoya, 1982;San
312 Miguel, 1985;Serrada-Hierro, 1991). The following measures are proposed to maintain
313 biodiversity in *Habitat I: 9230- Quercus pyrenaica, rebollo oak*:

314 - Conversion by thinning on coppice forest is proposed in high polewood (with
315 conservation status **B**: inconvenient), sapling (**A**: favourable), Coppice tall shrubs (**C**:
316 poor) during the first fifteen years. Forest management guidelines propose low-
317 intensity thinning on sprouts, less than 35% of the basal area for a period of 15 years
318 (Valbuena-Carabana *et al.*, 2008). It is worth investing money in these treatments in
319 order to reach favourable conservation status in the different types of stands, and to
320 ensure probable future acorn regeneration. Cattle can be released in these areas in
321 order to eat –and control– the sprouts thereby serving as a useful management tool
322 which combines environmental interests with those of the cattle owners (Huntsinger,
323 1996).

324 - Low polewood will not be managed over the next fifteen years even if its
325 conservation status is poor (**C**). These stands will be left to grow with the presence of
326 livestock, and only the best trees will survive; thus grazing is again used as a natural
327 thinning method.

328 - Oak shrubland will be tested. The main objective is to avoid the whole forest
329 becoming a coppice forest (**C**: poor) with no acorn regeneration. Oak shrubland will
330 therefore be fenced-in and tested (brushing out, bulldozer scalping, intensive and
331 medium thinning, no treatment) to evaluate the different possible evolutions.

332 - For *Habitat II: 9340- Quercus ilex subsp. rotundifolia forests* some pruning, in this
333 reduced habitat, is planned over the next fifteen years to improve its inconvenient
334 conservation status (B).

335

336 **Conclusion**

337

338 Different management techniques are being used in the implementation of the
339 Natura 2000 network in order to achieve favourable conservation status. However, this
340 process is slow and the European Member States need new methodologies and ideas. An
341 accurate and well-defined G.I.S. map of stands (Phase 1) showing their conservation
342 status and by extension, that of the habitats (Phase 2) is a useful tool for determining
343 forest management measures to ensure biodiversity in Natura 2000 areas. Although the
344 main objective is conservation rather than timber production, a detailed analysis of the
345 area is required. The division of the area into different types of stands provides the forest
346 manager with an accurate knowledge of the area, and more so when the conservation
347 status is shown on G.I.S. maps. Furthermore, this method of management by stands offers
348 flexibility, which is not provided by traditional methods of regeneration. It meets today's
349 requirements, both for society as a whole, and for the objectives established for the areas
350 in the Natura 2000 network.

351 The purpose is to achieve favourable conservation status; this can be done in the
352 study area by converting coppice forest into high forest. Livestock cannot be removed
353 due to possible pressure from cattle owners, and a sustainable solution is therefore
354 required for these areas. The proposed forestry measures use cattle as part of the solution
355 –rather than a drawback– for ensuring biodiversity.

356 In view of the fact that around 20% of Spanish forest is coppice forest *Quercus ilex* is
357 the most common (57%), followed by *Quercus pyrenaica* (17%) the forestry treatments
358 proposed in this paper can be applied not only in the study area but also in habitats with
359 similar problems in many other Natura 2000 forest sites.

360

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367

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369

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538 **Tables**

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PARAMETER	Type of cover and forest structure.
CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Basic forest management systems (High forest, coppice with standards, coppice forest). ▪ Stand structure (even-aged forest, composite forest, uneven-aged forest). ▪ Stand age (thicket, polewood, high forest) <p>- Meadows (man-made open stands or forest stands)</p>
CLASIFICATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coppice forest: thicket, polewood and high forest from stump. ▪ Composite forest. ▪ High forest: upgrowth, sapling, ticket, low polewood, high polewood, sapling , middle size trunk and standard tree. <p>- Not woodland areas: pasture, shrubland and rocks.</p>

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Table 1. – Criteria to distinguish stands in terms of forest structure.

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PARAMETER	Possible future forest management
CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- With or without forest management in the planned period.- Protected fauna areas, micro-reserves of flora and/or fauna and recreational areas.
CLASSIFICATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- High forest / reforestation.- Forest treatments: clearing, pruning or thinning.- Preparatory cutting, seed cutting, regenerative cutting, final cutting.- Clear-cutting, uniform shelterwood cutting, selection cutting, group shelterwood cutting, selective tree felling, coppice with standards.- Without treatment.- Special stands.

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Table 2. – Criteria to distinguish stands in terms of future forest management.

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Final values \bar{v} (for \bar{s} or H)	Conservation status
$\bar{v} > 2.2$	A: Favourable or good conservation status
$2.2 \leq \bar{v} < 1.6$	B: Inconvenient conservation status
$\bar{v} \leq 1.6$	C: Poor conservation status

Table 3. – Classification of conservation status.

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Habitat	Type of stand	Vital function	Restoration	Floral Richness	Structure	Conservation status (stands)	Conservation status (habitat)
	s_j	(f ₁)	(f ₂)	(f ₃)	(f ₄)	\bar{s}_j	H
Habitat I (<i>Quercus pyrenaica</i> $A_I=673,01$)	Oak shrubland ($A_1=77,91\text{Ha}$)	1	3	1	1	C (1,5)	$H_I =$ C (1,27)
	Low polewood ($A_2=218,06\text{Ha}$)	1	2	1	1	C (1,25)	
	High polewood ($A_3=112,25\text{Ha}$)	2	2	2	2	B (2)	
	Sapling ($A_4=96,79\text{Ha}$)	3	3	2	2	A (2,5)	
	Coppice tall shrubs ($A_5=168\text{Ha}$)	2	2	1	1	C (1,5)	
Habitat II (<i>Quercus ilex</i> $A_{II}=15,1\text{Ha}$)	High Forest ($A_6=15,1\text{Ha}$)	1	2	2	2	B (1,75)	$H_{II} =$ B (1,75)

Table 4. – Conservation status by stand and by habitat.

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Figure 1. – Location of the study area.

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Figure 2. – Types of stands.

Figure 3. – Conservation status of stands.

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Figure 4. – Conservation status of oak shrubland (C: poor).

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Figure 5. – Conservation status of sampling (A: favourable).